

Kinetics and Mechanism of Oxidation of Amino Acids by Dichloramine-B

P. JAGAN MOHANA RAO and B. THIMME GOWDA*

Department of Post-Graduate Studies and Research in Chemistry, Mangalore University, Mangalagangothri-574 199

Manuscript received 30 December 1991, accepted 9 July 1992

Kinetics of oxidations of several amino acids (AA) (glycine, alanine, valine, leucine and phenylalanine) by dichloramine-B (DCB) have been studied in aquo-methanol (1 : 1, v/v) in the presence of perchloric acid. The reactions show two ranges in $[HClO_4]$. In the first range of $[HClO_4]$ (0.0005–0.005 mol dm⁻³), the oxidations exhibit second order kinetics in [DCB], fractional order in [AA] and inverse fractional order in $[H^+]$. In the second range of $[HClO_4]$ (0.005–0.10 mol dm⁻³) also the reactions show similar dependence in [DCB], but generally show first order kinetics in [AA] and inverse first order in $[H^+]$. The rates slightly increase with increasing ionic strength, while decrease with increase in methanol composition of the solvent. Addition of benzenesulphonamide, the reduced product of the oxidant, has no significant effect on the rates of oxidations. Suitable mechanisms consistent with the observed results have been considered and the related rate laws deduced. Coefficients of the rate limiting steps have been calculated at different temperatures and the activation parameters corresponding to these constants are also computed. The validity of the mechanisms is tested by recalculating the rate constants from the deduced rate laws as [AA] and $[H^+]$ are varied. Reasonably good agreement between the recalculated values and the experimental constants provide support to the proposed mechanisms.

Oxidative decarboxylation of amino acids is of interest both from a pure chemical point of view and from the point of view of its bearing on the mechanism of amino acid metabolism¹. The free amino acids take part in numerous metabolic reactions. Specific metabolic role of amino acids include the biosynthesis of polypeptides and proteins and synthesis of nucleotides etc. Thus the mechanism of analogous non-enzymatic chemical processes of oxidative decarboxylation of amino acids is a potential area for intensive experimentation. As a part of our mechanistic studies with amino acids and other biologically active substrates^{2,3}, we report herein the kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of several amino acids by *N,N*-dichlorobenzene sulphonamide in aquo-methanol (1 : 1, v/v) medium in the presence of perchloric acid.

Results and Discussion

The kinetics of oxidations of Gly, Ala, Val, Leu and Phe by dichloramine-B in aquo-methanol (1 : 1, v/v) were studied under varying conditions: [DCB] (0.0005–0.004 mol dm⁻³), [AA] (0.005–0.10 mol dm⁻³) and $[HClO_4]$ (0.0005–0.10 mol dm⁻³). The results are shown in Tables 1–3 and Figs. 1–3. The kinetics of oxidations showed two ranges in $[H^+]$ (0.0005–0.005 mol dm⁻³ and 0.005–0.10 mol dm⁻³). The rates decreased with increase in $[HClO_4]$ with varying inverse dependences in $[H^+]$ in the two ranges.

Oxidation in the $[HClO_4]$ range (0.0005–0.005 mol dm⁻³): At fixed $[AA]_0$ and $[HClO_4]$, the second order plots ($1/[DCB]$ vs time) were linear at least for two-half lives. The pseudo-second order rate constants (k_{obs}), computed from the plots, were unaffected by the changes in $[DCB]_0$ for

oxidations of Gly, Ala and Val. While they decreased slightly with increase in $[DCB]_0$ (Table 2), with Leu and Phe. But their 1.5-order plots ($1/\sqrt{[DCB]}$ vs time) were parallel at different $[DCB]_0$ (Fig. 1). At fixed $[DCB]_0$ and $[HClO_4]$, the rates increased

Fig. 1. Plots of (i) $1/[DCB]$ vs time and (ii) $1/[DCB]^{1/2}$ vs time; $150[AA]_0 = 10^3[HClO_4] = 3.0$ mol dm⁻³, solvent: water-methanol (1 : 1, v/v), $I = 0.30$ mol dm⁻³, temp. = 303 K; $10^3[DCB]_0$ (mol dm⁻³): (a) 0.5, (b) 1.0, (c) 2.0 and (d) 4.0.

with increase in $[AA]_0$ (Table 2) and the plots of $\log k_{obs}$ vs $\log [AA]_0$ were linear with varying slopes showing fractional order kinetics in $[AA]$. The results with Leu and Phe were systematically analysed. The kinetic orders in $[Leu]$ or $[Phe]$ and $[H^+]$ were determined from the first order, 1.5-order and second order plots at constant $[DCB]_0$. The magnitudes of values were almost the same.

Oxidation in the $[HClO_4]$ range (0.005–0.10 mol dm^{-3}): Oxidations of Gly, Ala and Val in the acid range >0.005 mol dm^{-3} showed pseudo-second order kinetics in $[DCB]$. The rates increased with increase in $[AA]_0$ with first order dependences in $[AA]$.

TABLE 1.—PSEUDO-SECOND ORDER RATE CONSTANTS (k_{obs}) FOR THE OXIDATION OF AMINO ACIDS (AA) BY DICHLORAMINE-B (DCB) IN AQUO-METHANOL (1 : 1, v/v) MEDIUM IN PRESENCE OF PERCHLORIC ACID

Temp. = 303 K ($I=0.30$ mol dm^{-3})		$10^3 k_b$ (dm^3 mol $^{-1}$ s $^{-1}$)				
$10^3 [HClO_4]$ mol dm^{-3}	pH ^a	Gly	Ala	Val	Leu	Phe ^c
0.5	3.16	9.7	—	—	—	—
1.0	3.08	10.5	17.1	4.9	12.2	6.8
2.0	2.92	18.7	14.9	4.4	9.9	4.9
3.0	2.70	—	13.6	—	7.3	3.8
5.0	2.32	6.8	9.4	2.9	6.5	3.1
10.0	2.04	3.9 (9.4)	5.1	2.3	5.3	1.9
20.0	1.78	1.7 (6.1)	2.2	1.1	4.2	0.6
30.0	1.64	—	1.4	0.51	—	—
50.0	1.39	0.52 (2.1)	0.95	0.31	2.8	—
100.0	1.02	0.34 (0.88)	0.75	0.24	—	—

^aMeasured values at different $[HClO_4]$. ^b $10^3 [DCB]_0 = 50$ $[AA]_0 = 1.0$ mol dm^{-3} . ^c $10^3 [DCB]_0 = 100 [AA]_0 = 2.0$ mol dm^{-3} , values in parenthesis are for $10^3 [AA] = 5.0$ mol dm^{-3} at 308 K.

The rates increased slightly with increasing ionic strength while decreased with increase in methanol composition of the solvent, in both the ranges. Addition of benzenesulphonamide, the reduced product of the oxidant, had no significant effect on the rates of oxidations. The rates were

measured at different temperatures (293–313 K). Coefficients of the rate-determining steps have been calculated at each temperature. The activation parameters corresponding to these constants are also computed from the Arrhenius and Eyring plots (Table 4).

Mechanism of oxidations :

The following equilibria exist in partial aqueous solutions of dichloramine-B²,

Hence the probable reactive species in aqueous methanol solutions of dichloramine-B are $PhSO_2-NCl_2$, $PhSO_2NHCl$ and $HOCl$.

Amino acids are known to exist in the cationic forms ($RCH(NH_3^+)COOH$, SH^+) in strongly acidic medium, which change over to zwitterionic forms ($RCH(NH_3^+)COO^-$, S^0), as the pH of the reaction medium is raised and finally to anionic forms ($RCHNH_2COO^-$, S^-) in strongly alkaline medium¹. The oxidation of amino acids by dichloramine-B in aquo-methanol medium showed two ranges in $[H^+]$ (0.0005–0.005 mol dm^{-3} and 0.005–0.10 mol dm^{-3}) and varied kinetic behaviour as described earlier.

In the $[HClO_4]$ range, 0.0005–0.005 mol dm^{-3} : The kinetics of second order in $[DCB]$, fractional order in $[AA]$ and inverse fractional order in $[H^+]$ observed in this acid range may be explained by a mechanism shown in Scheme 1.

TABLE 2.—PSEUDO-SECOND ORDER RATE CONSTANTS (k_{obs}) FOR THE OXIDATION OF AMINO ACIDS (AA) BY DICHLORAMINE-B (DCB) IN AQUO-METHANOL (1 : 1, v/v) MEDIUM IN THE PRESENCE OF PERCHLORIC ACID AT 303 K ($I=0.30$ mol dm^{-3})

$10^3 [DCB]_0$ mol dm^{-3}	$10^3 [AA]_0$ mol dm^{-3}	$10^3 k_{obs}$ (dm^3 mol $^{-1}$ s $^{-1}$) at $10^3 [HClO_4]$ (mol dm^{-3})							
		Gly		Ala		Val		Leu	Phe
		0.10	2.0	0.20	1.0	0.50	3.0		
Effect of varying $[DCB]_0$									
0.30	2.0 (5.0) ^a	10.3	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
0.5	2.0 (5.0)	10.2	6.1	14.8	5.0	2.9	0.50	9.3	6.7
1.0	2.0 (5.0)	10.5	6.1	14.9	5.1	2.9	0.51	7.3	4.6
2.0	2.0 (5.0)	10.6	5.9	14.9	5.1	2.8	0.51	6.5	3.1
4.0	2.0 (5.0)	—	—	15.2	5.2	2.9	0.53	5.6	2.8
Effect of varying $[AA]_0$									
1.0 (2.0) ^b	0.5	3.9	—	8.7	1.1	2.1	—	2.0	—
1.0 (2.0)	1.0	7.0	—	11.5	2.2	2.5	—	3.7	—
1.0 (2.0)	1.5	—	—	—	—	—	0.38	—	1.9
1.0 (2.0)	2.0	10.5	—	14.9	5.1	2.9	0.51	7.3	3.1
1.0 (2.0)	3.0	12.6	3.7	16.8	6.5	3.3	0.98	—	3.8
1.0 (2.0)	4.0	—	—	—	—	—	—	10.1	5.4
1.0 (2.0)	5.0	—	6.1	20.8	9.7	4.4	1.51	—	—
1.0 (2.0)	8.0	—	11.0	—	—	—	—	—	—
1.0 (2.0)	10.0	—	13.5	—	—	—	—	—	—

Values in parenthesis are for : ^aGly at $[H^+] = 0.02$ mol dm^{-3} and 308 K, ^bphenylalanine (Phe)

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF VARYING SOLVENT COMPOSITION OF REACTION MEDIUM, IONIC STRENGTH AND ADDITION OF THE REDUCED PRODUCT, BENZENESULPHONAMIDE (BSA) ON THE RATES OF OXIDATION OF AMINO ACIDS BY DICHLORAMINE-B (DCB) IN AQUO-METHANOL (1 : 1, v/v) MEDIUM* IN PRESENCE OF PERCHLORIC ACID AT 303 K

MeOH %	$10k_{obs} \text{ (dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}) \text{ at } 10^3[\text{HClO}_4] \text{ (mol dm}^{-3})$								
	Gly		Ala		Val		Leu	Pheb	
	0.1	2.0 ^a	0.2	1.0	0.5	3.0			
40	12.3	7.4	22.4	7.6	4.5	0.62	9.4	3.9	
50	10.5	6.1	14.9	5.1	2.9	0.51	7.3	3.1	
60	5.9	3.7	9.8	3.4	2.2	0.42	5.6	1.2	
70	4.3	—	—	2.4	—	—	4.1	—	
10I mol dm ⁻³	Gly		Ala	Val	Leu 10 ³ [BSA] mol dm ⁻³		Gly	Ala	Val
	0.1	2.0 ^a	1.0	0.5			0.1	2.0 ^a	1.0
1.0	8.4	4.8	4.9	2.8	6.8	1.0	10.5	6.0	5.0
3.0	10.5	6.1	5.1	2.9	7.3	2.0	10.4	6.0	4.8
5.0	12.0	7.4	5.4	3.1	7.7	4.0	10.3	5.8	4.5

*10³[DCB]₀=50[AA]₀=1.0 mol dm⁻³. ^a10³[AA]₀=5.0 mol dm⁻³, Temp. =308 K.
^b10³[DCB]₀=10³[AA]₀=2.0 mol dm⁻³.

Applying the steady state approximation to the intermediate X, we have

$$[X] = \frac{k_1[\text{PhSO}_2\text{NCl}_2]_0[S]}{k_{-1}[\text{H}^+] + k_2[\text{PhSO}_2\text{NCl}_2] + k_1[S]} \quad (3)$$

where, $[\text{PhSO}_2\text{NCl}_2] = [\text{PhSO}_2\text{NCl}_2]_0 - [X]$ and $[S]_0 \approx [S]$. Since k_2 is small and $[S] \gg [\text{PhSO}_2\text{NCl}_2]$, $k_2[\text{PhSO}_2\text{NCl}_2]$ is negligibly small compared with other terms in the denominator, then equation (3) becomes

$$[X] = \frac{k_1[\text{PhSO}_2\text{NCl}_2]_0[S]}{k_{-1}[\text{H}^+] + k_1[S]} = \frac{K_1[\text{DCB}]_0[S]}{[\text{H}^+] + K_1[S]} \quad (4)$$

where, $K_1 = k/k_{-1}$. The rate of the reaction is then given by equation (5),

$$-\frac{d[\text{DCB}]}{dt} = k_2[\text{DCB}][X] = \frac{K_1 k_2 [\text{DCB}]_0 [\text{DCB}][S]}{[\text{H}^+] + K_1[S]} \quad (5)$$

If we now make further assumption that $[\text{DCB}]_0 \approx [\text{DCB}]^2$, then the rate law (5) becomes

$$-\frac{d[\text{DCB}]}{dt} = \frac{K_1 k_2 [\text{DCB}]^2 [S]}{[\text{H}^+] + K_1[S]} \quad (6)$$

Rearranging equation (6), we have

$$-\frac{1}{[\text{DCB}]^2} \frac{d[\text{DCB}]}{dt} = \frac{K_1 k_2 [S]}{[\text{H}^+] + K_1[S]} \quad (7)$$

But left-hand-side of equation (7) may be written as

$$-\frac{1}{[\text{DCB}]^2} \frac{d[\text{DCB}]}{dt} = \frac{d\{1/[\text{DCB}]\}}{dt} = k_{obs}$$

Hence equation (7) becomes

$$k_{obs} = \frac{K_1 k_2 [S]}{[\text{H}^+] + K_1[S]} \quad (8)$$

or

$$\frac{1}{k_{obs}} = \frac{[\text{H}^+]}{K_1 k_2 [S]} + \frac{1}{k_2} \quad (9)$$

The plots of $1/k_{obs}$ vs $1/[\text{AA}]$ (Fig. 2) and $1/k_{obs}$ vs $[\text{H}^+]$ were linear with finite intercepts on the ordinates, in conformity with the rate law (9). The constant k_2 was calculated from the intercept of

Fig 2. Plots of (i) $1/k_{obs}$ vs $1/[\text{AA}]$; $10^3[\text{DCB}]_0$ (mol dm⁻³)=1.0 (Gly, Ala, Val, Leu), 2.0 (Phe), $10^3[\text{HClO}_4]$ (mol dm⁻³)=1.0 (Gly), 2.0 (Ala), 3.0 (Leu), 5.0 (Val, Phe), solvent: water-methanol (1 : 1, v/v), $I=0.30$ mol dm⁻³, temp. =303 K; and (ii) $1/k_{obs}$ vs $[\text{HClO}_4]$, $10^3[\text{DCB}]_0$ (mol dm⁻³)=1.0 (Gly, Ala, Val, Leu), 2.0 (Phe), $10^3[\text{AA}]_0=2.0$ mol dm⁻³, Temp. =303 K, solvent: water-methanol (1 : 1, v/v), $I=0.30$ mol dm⁻³, temp. =303 K.

the former plot (Table 4). The equilibrium constant (K_1) was calculated from the slope of the plot by

TABLE 4—COEFFICIENTS OF RATE-DETERMINING STEPS AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES AND ACTIVATION PARAMETERS FOR OXIDATION OF AMINO ACIDS (AA) BY DICHLORAMINE-B (DCB) IN AQUO-METHANOL (1 : 1, v/v) MEDIA

[AA]	k_2 (dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)				Calculated from k_2 values				
	298K	303K	308K	313K	log A	E_a kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔH^\ddagger kJ mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta S^\ddagger$ JK ⁻¹	ΔG^\ddagger kJ mol ⁻¹
Gly	2.00	2.44	2.67	2.86	4.1	21.5	18.4	177.0	72.0
Ala	1.41	1.92	2.63	3.13	7.6	42.5	43.8	95.0	72.6
Val	0.28	0.40	0.53	0.91	10.4	61.7	57.7	59.9	75.9
Leu	1.43	2.86	4.00	—	10.2	56.7	46.3	83.6	71.6
Phe	1.67	2.00	2.50	3.33	6.9	38.3	30.5	138.6	72.5

inserting the value k_2 ($K_1 = 0.038$ (Gly), 0.33 (Ala), 0.32 (Val), 0.045 (Leu) and 0.033 (Phe)).

Further, [AA] was varied at different temperatures (293–313 K) and the values of k_2 were calculated at each temperature (Table 4). The activation parameters were then calculated from the plots of $\log k_2$ vs $1/T$ and $\log (k_2/T)$ vs $1/T$ (Table 4). The constants K_1 and k_2 computed from the plots of $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $1/[AA]$ were employed to recalculate the rate constants from the rate law (9) as $[H^+]$ was varied. Similarly, the values of K_1 and k_2 calculated from the plots of $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $[H^+]$ were used to recalculate the constants from the rate law as [AA] was varied. The calculated constants compared with the experimental values (Table 5). Reasonable agreement between the two sets of values tests the validity of the rate law and thus provides support to the suggested mechanism.

TABLE 5—COMPARISON OF RECALCULATED VALUES AND EXPERIMENTAL RATE CONSTANTS FOR OXIDATION OF AMINO ACIDS BY DICHLORAMINE-B IN AQUO-METHANOL (1 : 1, v/v) MEDIUM

$10^2[AA]$ mol dm ⁻³	$10k$ (dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)				
	Observed/Recalculated ^a				
	Gly	Ala	Val	Leu	Phe
0.5	3.9 (4.3)	8.7 7.0	2.1 1.9	2.0 3.5	—
1.0	7.0 (7.6)	11.5 10.8	2.5 2.3	3.7 5.1	—
1.5	—	—	—	—	1.9 (2.3)
2.0	10.5 (10.4)	14.9 14.8	2.9 3.0	7.3 7.4	3.1 3.1
3.0	12.6 (11.3)	16.8 16.9	3.3 3.5	—	3.8 3.9
4.0	—	—	—	10.1 (9.1)	5.4 4.81
5.0	—	20.8 (19.1)	4.4 4.3	—	—
$10^2[HClO_4]$ mol dm ⁻³					
1.0	10.5 (10.5)	17.1 16.7	4.9 4.6	12.2 13.4	6.8 7.2
2.0	8.7 (7.9)	14.9 14.8	4.4 4.2	9.9 8.9	4.9 4.9
3.0	—	13.6 13.2	2.9 2.9	7.3 6.9	3.8 3.6
5.0	6.8 (6.1)	9.4 10.2	2.3 2.1	6.5 4.7	3.1 2.8

^aValues recalculated from the rate law (10).

In the $[HClO_4]$ range, 0.005–0.10 mol dm⁻³. As the $[HClO_4]$ is increased, the equilibrium,

becomes significant. Hence a slightly modified mechanism (Scheme 2) explains the observed kinetic results in this acid range.

Applying steady state hypothesis to the intermediate, X', the following rate laws have been deduced.

$$\frac{d[DCB]}{dt} = \frac{K_4 k_5 [DCB]^2 [S]}{1 + K_4 [S]} \quad (11)$$

or

$$k_{\text{obs}} = \frac{K_4 k_5 [S]}{1 + K_4 [S]} \quad (12)$$

$$\text{But we have, } [S] = \frac{K_3 [H^+]}{[H^+]} \quad (13)$$

Therefore equation (12) takes the form,

$$k_{\text{obs}} = \frac{K_3 K_4 k_5 [SH^+]}{[H^+] + K_3 K_4 [SH^+]} \quad (14)$$

If the product $K_3 K_4$ is small, then rate law (14) will take the form,

$$k_{\text{obs}} = K_4 k_5 [S] = K_3 K_4 k_5 \frac{[SH^+]}{[H^+]} \quad (15)$$

The plots of k_{obs} vs [AA] and k_{obs} vs $1/[H^+]$ were reasonably linear with almost zero intercept on the ordinates (Fig. 3) in accordance with rate law (15).

It is observed that the pseudo-second order rate constants with Leu and Phe decreased with increase in [DCB]. This may be due to the operation of two competitive rate-determining steps. In addition to step (ii) in Scheme 1, $X + PhSO_2NCl_2 \rightarrow \text{Products}$ (second order pathway in [DCB]), another competitive first order pathway, $X + H_2O \rightarrow \text{Products}$, may be operative. Thus the kinetics in [DCB] vary between 1 and 2. It is evident therefore that the rate constants computed from second order plots decrease with increase in [DCB] and pseudo-first order constants increase with increase in [DCB]₀. This was further confirmed by the fact that 1.5-order plots in [DCB] ($1/\sqrt{[DCB]}$ vs time) were almost parallel at different [DCB]₀ (Fig. 1).

Fig. 3. Plots of (i) k_{obs} vs $[AA]$, $10^3[DCB]_0=1.0$ mol dm^{-3} , $10^2[HClO_4]$ (mol dm^{-3}) = 1.0 (Ala), 2.0 (Gly), 3.0 (Val); solvent: water-methanol (1 : 1, v/v), $I=0.30$ mol dm^{-3} , temp = 303 K; and (ii) k_{obs} vs $1/[HClO_4]$, $10^3[DCB]_0=1.0$ mol dm^{-3} , $10^2[AA]$ (mol dm^{-3}) = 2.0 (Ala, Val), 5.0 (Gly)

A typical detailed mechanism of oxidation of amino acids by dichloramine-B is shown in Scheme 3.

The observed negative dielectric effect on the rates of oxidations (Table 3), is in conformity with Amis-Jaffee equation for dipolar molecule-dipolar molecule interaction⁴,

$$\log k_D = \log k \propto - \frac{2\mu_1\mu_2}{2.303 k_B T r^3 D} \quad (16)$$

where, k_D and k are the rate constants in media of dielectric constants D and ∞ respectively, k_B is the Boltzmann constant, μ_1 and μ_2 are the permanent moments on the dipoles, r is the distance of approach for the dipoles and T the absolute temperature.

The plots of $\log k_{obs}$ vs $1/D$ were linear with negative slopes in accordance equation (16).

Experimental

N,N-Dichlorobenzene sulphonamide, abbreviated as dichloramine-B (DCB), was prepared by the chlorination of chloramine-B⁵. The stock solution (~ 0.10 mol dm^{-3}) of the oxidant in pure methanol was prepared and standardised by iodometric

Scheme 3

method and preserved in amber coloured bottles. Chromatographically pure amino acids: glycine (Gly), alanine (Ala), valine (Val), leucine (Leu) and phenylalanine (Phe) (Sisco) were further assayed by the standard methods reported elsewhere⁶. Aqueous stock solutions (0.1 mol dm^{-3}) of the amino acids (AA) were prepared in double-distilled water. The ionic strength of the reaction medium was kept at 0.30 mol dm^{-3} with a concentrated aqueous solution of sodium perchlorate. All other reagents used were of accepted grades of purity.

Kinetic measurements: Kinetic studies were made in glass stoppered pyrex boiling tubes under pseudo-second order conditions with $[AA] \gg [DCB]$. The reactions were initiated by the quick addition of measured amounts of oxidant solution (0.0005–0.004 mol dm^{-3}), thermostated at a desired temperature, to solutions containing required amounts of amino acid (0.005–0.10 mol dm^{-3}), perchloric

acid (0.0005–0.10 mol dm⁻³), methanol and water (to maintain 1 : 1, v/v, water-methanol composition), equilibrated at the same temperature. The progress of the reactions was monitored for two half-lives by iodometric estimation of unreacted oxidant at regular time intervals. The pseudo-second order rate constants (k_{obs}) were calculated by the graphical methods and the values were reproducible within $\pm 4\%$ error.

Stoichiometry and product analysis: The stoichiometries of DCB-amino acid reactions were determined in 1 : 1 (v/v) water-methanol medium in the presence of varying [HClO₄] (0.0005–0.10 mol dm⁻³) by equilibrating varying ratios of [DCB]₀ to [AA]₀ at room temperature for different intervals of time. The products were found to be CO₂ and the corresponding nitrile⁷. The test solution was boiled with hydroxylamine hydrochloride in methanol (1 ml) and KOH in methanol (1 ml) for 2 min. The solution was cooled and 5% ferric chloride hexahydrate in ethanol (1 ml) was added. Sufficient 2 M methanolic HCl was added to dissolve any ferric hydroxide. A red colour showed the presence of nitrile. It was further observed that the parent nitrile, methyl nitrile (CH₃CN) did not undergo further reactions with the oxidant under the reaction conditions.

Benzenesulphonamide (BSA), the reduced product of the oxidant was detected by tlc⁸ employing ether-chloroform-n-butanol (2 : 2 : 1, v/v) as solvent and iodine as detecting reagent ($R_f=0.88$).

The observed 1 : 1 molar stoichiometry may be represented by the following equation,

where, R = H(Gly), CH₃(Ala), (CH₃)₂CH(Val), (CH₃)₂CHCH₂(Leu), C₆H₅(Phe). The oxidation of amino acids by DCB did not induce polymerisation of acrylonitrile.

References

1. H. D. JAKUBKE and H. JESCHKEIT, "Amino Acids, Peptides and Proteins", Wiley, New York, 1977.
2. B. T. GOWDA and D. S. MAHADEVAPPA, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 2*, 1983, 323 and references therein.
3. B. T. GOWDA and J. I. BHAT, *Tetrahedron*, 1987, **43**, 2119; *Int. J. Chem. Kinet.*, 1989, **21**, 31; B. T. GOWDA and B. S. SHERIGARA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1987, **26**, 930; B. T. GOWDA and R. V. RAO, *Oxidn. Commun.*, 1988, **11**, 45, 149; *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 2*, 1988, 355; B. T. GOWDA and P. RAMACHANDRA, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 2*, 1989, 1067; *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci. (Chem. Sci.)*, 1990, **102**, 7; B. T. GOWDA and P. J. M. RAO, *Z. Phys. Chem. (N. F.)*, 1990.
4. E. S. AMIS, "Solvent Effects on Reaction Rates and Mechanisms", Academic, New York, 1966; P. ZUMAN and R. C. PATEL, "Techniques in Organic Reaction Kinetics", Wiley, New York, 1984.
5. H. S. YATHIRAJAN, D. S. MAHADEVAPPA and RANGASWAMY, *Talanta*, 1980, **27**, 52.
6. A. I. VOGEL, "Quantitative Organic Analysis", Longman and Green, London, 1958.
7. S. SOLOWAY and A. LIPSCHITZ, *Anal. Chem.*, 1952, **24**, 898.
8. E. STAHL, "Thin Layer Chromatography, A Laboratory Handbook", Springer, New York, 1969.